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V: “Of One Blood”: Ethiopian Counter Narrative to the Racial Contract

Charles Mills’ criticism of social contract theory, *The Racial Contract*, enhances the novel *Of One Blood* by Pauline Hopkins by providing a conceptual framework of global white supremacy that the novel seeks to subvert. The novel was serialized in two volumes by the *Colored American Magazine* in 1902 and 1903, of which Hopkins was an editor. Written at the turn of the twentieth century during the Jim Crow era, the novel follows the adventure of Reuel Briggs, a mixed-race American, as he travels to Ethiopia to raid the country of lost and ancient treasures. In this back-to-Africa novel, the main character descends into Africa and uncovers the twisted history of his family as well as the advanced, hidden city of Telassar that he is the long-lost ruler of. Although Mills does not discuss works of an aesthetic nature, literature affirms his argument and has a larger role impacting society as a whole. In the novel *Of One Blood*, Hopkins creates the fantastical, utopian city of Telassar to operate as a counternarrative for black Americans against the global white supremacist system Mills puts forth in *The Racial Contract*.

Reuel Briggs is a brilliant, yet destitute, Harvard medical student who passes for white. He reluctantly attends a performance of the Fisk Jubilee Singers with his affluent, Southern, white best friend Aubrey Livingston. The lead singer, Dianthe Lusk, nearly dies in a train accident later that night but Reuel is able to miraculously revive her. Dianthe suffers from amnesia and has no recollection of her previous life. Reuel falls in love with Dianthe and they marry in secret. He is unable to provide for his new bride since no one will hire him because of a rumor about his racial identity. Aubrey sets him up on a dangerous yet lucrative British-led archaeological expedition to Africa. In Meroe, Reuel literally stumbles upon the ancient, hidden city of Telassar, which he is recognized as the long-awaited heir to the Ethiopian throne. Meanwhile, Aubrey faked Dianthe's death and forced her to marry him at his ancestral home.

They first travel to Egypt, but once in Ethiopia, Reuel receives news that Dianthe died. He disappears into Meroe's ruins to die, but is kidnapped and awakens in a luxurious palace within the hidden city of Telassar, built by the inhabitants of Meroe. Reuel is revealed to be the long-awaited King Ergamenes, who is destined to marry Queen Candace and bring about glory for Ethiopia once more. Utilizing Telassar's mystical powers and advanced technology, Reuel spies on Aubrey and learns that he faked Dianthe's death to marry her in secret. Enraged, Reuel and his companions return to America to seek revenge. Dianthe regains her memory and meets Hannah, an elderly formerly enslaved woman of the Livingston family. Hannah confronts Dianthe, and tells her that she, Aubrey, and Reuel are all siblings, and that their mother, Mira, was an enslaved woman of Ethiopian descent. Aubrey was switched at birth as a newborn with the (dead) legitimate Livingston heir. With her memory and the truth come to light, Dianthe attempts to poison Aubrey, but he gains the upper-hand and forces Dianthe to drink the poison. Reuel arrives at the Livingston mansion just as Dianthe dies. In keeping with ancient Ethiopian

penalty for committing murder, Aubrey kills himself. At the conclusion of the novel Reuel returns to Telassar to serve as King Ergamenes and weds Queen Candace, teaching his people about Western culture.

Reuel's decision to pass for white reinforces an aesthetic norming of the body that is a consequence of the Racial Contract. His appearance has "superior physical endowments, but as yet he never had reason to count them blessings."⁸² Reuel was constantly worried about being outed as mixed, placing a strain on his ability to socialize and to work. But he chose mental strain over the known consequences of being mixed in a white supremacist society. He specifically had a "the nose was the aristocratic feature, although nearly spoiled by broad nostrils, of this remarkable young man; his skin was white, but of a tint suggesting olive, an almost swallow color which is the mark of strong, melancholic temperaments."⁸³ Reuel's physical descriptions are racially coded cues for blackness and operate within Eurocentric beauty standards. For Mills, "the white body is the somatic norm, so that in early racist theories one finds not only moral but aesthetic judgements, with beautiful and fair races pitted against ugly and dark races."⁸⁴ Moreover, Reuel's "aristocratic nose" hints at the mixing of bloodlines due to white features that could not have appeared any other way. The somatic norming of the white body alienates black people from their own body. This can literally be shown through Dianthe's amnesia. She forgets her entire identity, and because she is so light-skinned she passes for white when previously society identified her as black. Dianthe represents "a fate particularly painful for black women, who, like all women, will be valued chiefly by their physical appearance, which will generally be deemed to fall short of the Caucasoid or light-skinned ideal⁸⁵." Hopkins

⁸² Pauline Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, (Washington Square Press, 2004), 3.

⁸³ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 3.

⁸⁴ Charles W. Mills, *The Racial Contract*, (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 1997), 61.

⁸⁵ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 62.

attacks the assumption that light-skinned people would prefer to be white. The tragedy of Dianthe lies not in her biracial existence but rather in the fact that she was forced to pass for white. Reuel's decision to pass for white reinforces an aesthetic norming of the body that is a consequence of the Racial Contract.

The entire expedition was imperialist in nature, and as they traveled deeper into Ethiopia the group's perceptions reflected contemporary understandings held by the white polity. Everyone's interests were purely economic: to ravage the already crumbled ancient city of Meroe for its final treasures. Professor Stone told the men that because the city was the center of trade, "Meroe must have held vast treasuries... My theory is that somewhere under those pyramids we shall find invaluable records and immense treasure."⁸⁶ To them the city provided a quick and dirty way to take the land's natural resources and historical artifacts of an African civilization to profit for themselves, a group of white Americans. Even Reuel deemed of the fame and fortune that awaited him⁸⁷. Though fictional, the expedition holds up a mirror to European superiority of conquest. Mills argues that the Racial Contract is a historical actuality, located within "the series of events marking the creation of the modern world by European colonialism and the voyages of 'discovery' now increasingly and more appropriately called expeditions of conquest."⁸⁸ Repeating the actions of European colonists, Hopkins' characters remind readers of white dominance and the norming the white polity has created through the Racial Contract to imply that if a white man has not been *there*, culture and thus cognition has not taken place. Hopkins does this only to invert the colonial adventure story once Reuel "discovers" the hidden city of Telassar.

⁸⁶ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 87.

⁸⁷ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 37.

⁸⁸ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 20.

Hopkins describes the African landscape in a way that continues the Racial Contract’s norming and racing of space. Reuel also saw the African safari as majestic and peaceful. Looking across the grassland, “the caravan seemed to be the only living creature larger than a gazelle in the great solitude. Even Reuel was aroused to enthusiasm by the sight of a herd of these graceful creatures skimming the plain.”⁸⁹ He was mesmerized by the vast, uncivilized land. Reuel and the others wondered at the primitive setting, perfect for exotic beasts like the leopard. This rugged, untouched African landscape seemed to be untouched by Africans as well. Reuel thought “there is an intimate relation between the character of a country and that of its people, [he] realized vividly that the race who dwelt here must be different from those of the rest of the world.”⁹⁰ By implicitly connecting the continent’s landscapes with its people, Reuel thinks Africans to be primitive and uncivilized. This is exactly how Mills argues that the Racial Contract “demarcates civil and wild spaces” with Africa being the latter.⁹¹ Those spaces bleed into the civil and political, requiring “an active *spatial* struggle (this space is resistant) against the savage and barbaric, an advancing of the frontier against opposition, a Europeanization of the world.”⁹² The separation of spaces, reflected through the untouched landscape of Africa in comparison to the bustling societal spaces of Europe, reinforces the Racial Contract.

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Reuel stumbles into Telassar as if it were fate, to signal his rise to the throne as King Ergamenes who will usher in an era of African excellence. Reuel accidentally finds the path to Telassar through a pyramid, and is not greeted with violence by Telassarians, unlike other

⁸⁹ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 82.

⁹⁰ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 76.

⁹¹ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 41.

⁹² Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 43.

characters. Reuel meets the prime minister, Ai, who tells him that this is “the hidden city of Telassar. My people you will behold the direct descendants of the inhabitants of Meroe.”⁹³ Just as Professor Stone had theorized, the ancient city of Meroe was indeed prosperous, but to Reuel’s surprise the citizens are alive and thriving. Rather than being remnants of the past Telessarians exist in the present but intentionally conceal themselves, forcing Reuel, and the novel’s readers, to contemplate internalized racism about the dark continent.

As Reuel explores Telassar, Hopkins is utilizing conceptions of the aesthetic and splendor of Western antiquity, to say that in this version of history Telassar is the original creator of all that white civilization prides itself on. The hidden city is paradisaic in every detail, its buildings magnificent and beautiful, its lands fertile and lush, its people gorgeous and wise. Once he had adjusted, Reuel reflected that although, “Used as he was to the improvements and luxuries of life in modern Athens, he could not but acknowledge them as poor beside the combination of Oriental and ancient luxury that he now enjoyed. Was ever man more gorgeously housed than this?”⁹⁴ In comparison to the known wonders of antiquity, Telassar is far beyond them in everything. The city’s architecture enlists images of Greek-like qualities, with dome-shaped buildings made of white marble, vast columns, with courts and fountains.⁹⁵ All of the cultural and qualities of Telassar were the origins of and the blueprint for the West. He now realizes that “from Ethiopia came all the arts and cunning inventions that make [his] modern glory.”⁹⁶ This mystical, hidden city has architectural and aesthetic advancements that the modern world does not possess, forcing readers and Reuel to contemplate which civilization is “modern.” Reuel’s decision to pass as white, his refusal to think critically about racial concerns in American society,

⁹³ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 114.

⁹⁴ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 116.

⁹⁵ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 117

⁹⁶ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 129.

and his seeming lack of pride in his African heritage are abruptly confronted when he finds himself in this palace of grandeur. The hidden city operates as a space for opposition against the post-antebellum ideas of Africa as a whole. An undiscovered, unconquered city in African diaspora’s heritage and their strong self-valuation of blackness contest Racial Contract narratives of the past and present. By reimagining history, Hopkins affirms and subverts the historical claim of the white polity’s sociopolitical superiority made by the Racial Contract.

Almost immediately after enjoying the splendor of Telassar, Reuel is told he is the long-awaited King Ergamenes who is destined to revitalize their city; this revelation brings Hopkins’s utopian society to the attention of modern-day America. From a lineage lost to Telassar for centuries, Reuel was identified as royalty by his lotus shaped birthmark appearing on the breast of “every descendant of the royal line.”⁹⁷ Reuel’s mother Mira, a former enslaved

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woman, had passed on the birthmark, African blood, and mesmeric powers to him. He remembered, “It was tradition among those who had known him in childhood that he was descended from a race of African kings.”⁹⁸ Reuel had buried his family’s ancestry far away from his mind when he decided to pass for white and swear off all physical and cultural

identity to Africa. Now that Reuel had become aware of his African royal heritage and his newfound leadership over an unimaginable city, his ascension will lead their civilization to global prominence.

⁹⁷ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 120.

⁹⁸ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 126.

Mandy Reid wrote in “Utopia is in the Blood: The Bodily Utopias of Martin R. Delaney and Pauline Hopkins” that Hopkins “created King Ergamenes from Ethiopianism’s “two-part theory centered on Psalms 68:31: ‘Princes shall come out of Egypt; Ethiopia shall soon stretch forth her hands unto God’.”⁹⁹ The prophesied return of black civilization to the world stage is meant to bring hope for those within the African diaspora, a promise to rise up against their colonizers and oppressors to showcase black excellence and achievement. Ethiopianism predicts a new rise of Africa and its descendants to a previously glorious status, one they already had before white society took it away. For instance, Charlie Vance had heard:

From lands beyond unknown seas, to which many descendants of Ethiopia had been borne as slaves, should a king of ancient line — an offspring of that Ergamene [would] return and restore the former glory of the race. The preservation of this hidden city is for his reception.¹⁰⁰

The citizens of Meroe self-isolated themselves from enslavement and colonialism in order to protect what became Telassar for the future king. Meroe’s loss of prominence was divinely ordained. But this divine plan results in white global dominance, and on the other beneficiaries of that plan perpetuate injustice through their methods of maintaining white rule and their insistence on transhistorical white supremacy. *Of One Blood* and the hidden city critique the ways in which white civilization’s efforts to erase the historical fact of its debt and origins to Ethiopia, and to the continent as a whole, and it offers an opportunity to right historical wrongs.

Given the novel’s preoccupation with the notion of a shared humanity and equality, Telassar is presented as a symbol for what a just society would look like. The city showcases a fundamental belief in racial equality, as the citizens of Telassar are racially diverse and have roles within the city and governmental structures. Queen Candace guarded Telassar in the

⁹⁹ Mandy A. Reid, “Utopia Is in the Blood: The Bodily Utopias of Martin R. Delany and Pauline Hopkins,” *Utopian Studies*, vol. 22, no. 1, (2011), 91–103, <https://doi.org/10.5325/utopianstudies.22.1.0091>, 94.

¹⁰⁰ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 101-102.

absence of King Ergamenes; the city’s matriarchal structure embodies advanced African societal structures. An aesthetic masterpiece, Queen Candace carries their glorious cultural heritage and birthright since the royal bloodline is maternal. In that sense, the woman connects the past and present, and brings hope for Telassar’s future. Reuel is also excited about his pairing with Queen Candace, so that their union would “give to the world a dynasty of dark-skinned rulers, whose destiny should be to restore the prestige of an ancient people.”¹⁰¹ Not only is the city racially diverse, but its future rulers will be of dark skin, noticeably different from government leaders in America who are all white and actively work to disallow people of color from even running for elected office. Telassar acts as a shining example of what could be. Images of African and black inferiority are countered by the restored history and identity to diasporic people subjugated by whites, and highlight Africa’s contributions to world history and civilization.

Hopkins moves forward constructing utopian Telassar while simultaneously making jabs at white society’s epistemological ignorance that Mills views as foundational in the Racial Contract. In comparison to the Ethiopian city, the rest of the world is completely behind. Ai tells Reuel, “many things in [the] modern world are yet in its infancy,”¹⁰² and wonders if the rest of the world will ever catch up. The Racial Contract creates an epistemology of ignorance for its white signatories in relation to space. Significant cultural achievements, intellectual and technological progress is restricted only to those who possess cognition, and those within the African diaspora are denied both. It is only through discovery, expedition, and conquest that cognition can take place. As the opulence of Telassar is uncovered, it is clear that white civilization is the one who should be considered uncivilized and undeveloped, not the lands and the people of the African continent. The epistemological ethnocentrism Europe maintains is

¹⁰¹ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 139.

¹⁰² Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 119.

shattered. The site of a past, but also present, utopian community offers a beautiful city, extraordinarily intelligent and attractive citizens, and a celebratory black cultural history unknown to the wider world. Hopkins explicitly makes claims for epistemologies of African origin that surpass white European ones in their expertise.

Charlie Vance, a representative of white Americans and westerners in general, cannot even fathom Telassar's existence and his epistemology of ignorance collapses. When he is captured and brought to Telassar, he praises the people of his own race as "bold and venturesome, who known not fear if we can get a few more dollars and fresh information."¹⁰³ In response Ai, Telassar's Prime Minister asks, "They are people who count it a disgrace to bear my color; is it not so?"¹⁰⁴ Just after Hopkins' extensive description of Telassar's aesthetic, moral, spiritual, technological, and social superiority to the rest of the white dominated world, the question hits the irony of white presumption. Charlie exclaims in confusion how the city could be all built, maintained, and originated from African people.¹⁰⁵ While Ai is unbothered by Charlie's crumbling sense of self, Charlie's character resonates with white people whose conceptions of epistemology and history of the Racial Contract. For him and readers alike, white racism and imperialism had been naturalized by his experiences of black economic exploitation and dependence. His understandings of the world are dependent on the Racial Contract's version of history, and when forced to encounter the construction of his whiteness based on black inferiority, Charlie is stripped of his white power. Once in Telassar he is no longer an imperialist destined to dominate and take the riches of another culture. Ethiopian wealth cannot be fit back into the framework of Western domination.

¹⁰³ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 153.

¹⁰⁴ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 153.

¹⁰⁵ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 99.

The expedition's leader, Professor Stone believed Ethiopia to be the epicenter of civilization, and through him, Hopkins contests Western beliefs of human civilization. Mandy Reid's article views Hopkins' novel as a way to "real-world racial politics and prejudice. The article argued Hopkins "adapted and transformed the dominant discourse of the contemporary sciences of heredity."¹⁰⁶ During one of the caravan nights, he explains to Reuel and Charlie that "it is a fact that Egypt drew from Ethiopia all the arts, sciences and knowledge of which she was mistress" and hence that in Ethiopia lay the foundation head of European civilizations, since they had began from Egypt.¹⁰⁷ Stone even theorizes "that black was the original color of man in prehistoric times... placing the Ethiopian as the primal race."¹⁰⁸ Human history began and spread from Ethiopia. Similar to Reid's perspective, Jalondra Davis views Ethiopianism in her article, as a "cyclical view of black history that identifies African diasporas as descendants of a great African civilization."¹⁰⁹ Hopkins utilizes speculative fiction to re-envision history, and through the narrative is speaking to scientific and social discourses that center whites as the beginning of humans, not black people from Africa, thus proving their inherent superiority.

Reuel's racial identity climaxes with the knowledge of a shared parentage with Dianthe and Aubrey. At Aubrey's ancestral home, which is a plantation, Dianthe is told by Aunt Hannah that she, Reuel, and Aubrey are the children of Mira, an enslaved Ethiopian woman on the Livingston plantation. Their family history speaks to the twisted, rottenness of the institution of enslavement, and how oppression can be inherited. Aunt Hannah defeatingly told Dianthe that "Dese things jes; got to happen in slavery."¹¹⁰ Hopkins' conceptions of race and bloodlines fights

¹⁰⁶ Reid, "Utopia Is in the Blood: The Bodily Utopias of Martin R. Delany and Pauline Hopkins," 94.

¹⁰⁷ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 87

¹⁰⁸ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 88.

¹⁰⁹ Jalondra Davis, "Utopia and the Gendered Past in Pauline Hopkins' *Of One Blood; Or, The Hidden Self*," *MOSF Journal of Science Fiction*, vol. 3, no. 1, (2019), 7-20, <https://publish.lib.umd.edu/?journal=scifi&page=article&op=view&path%5B%5D=49&path%5B%5D=96>, 9.

¹¹⁰ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 176.

back against the decision by the United States Supreme Court in *Plessy v. Ferguson* (1896), which legitimized the “one drop” rule, by showing the social construction of race through her characters. Dianthe was light-skinned enough to pass, but chose to identify with her blackness; Reuel chose to hide his racial identity; and Aubrey lived an epistemically disadvantaged but materially advantaged life only to die with black blood in his veins and on his mind. Molly Godfrey wrote “*Of One Blood: Humanism, Race, and Gender in Post-Reconstruction Law and Literature*” on how the novel addresses pseudo-scientific discourses that insist on black inferiority. Hopkins’ novel reminds readers that both imperialism and segregation were used by the Racial Contract to embrace naturalized notions of racial difference. As long as black blood is hidden, “the idea of human brotherhood functions as a duplicitous tool that maintains the exclusionary injustice of slavery in a new guise,”¹¹¹ and black Americans will never be able to rise against their oppressors. Since the Racial Contract is constantly being rewritten, it keeps history invisible and promotes naturalized perceptions of black inferiority. Hopkins’ concerns in *Of One Blood* lie primarily in exposing and unraveling the entangled genealogies of blacks and whites, the irrefutable evidence that they were literally, biologically, “of one blood” and how that fact subverts the Racial Contract as explained by Mills.

The novel’s full title, *Of One Blood; Or, the Hidden Self* contests dominant notions concerning race and blood that have long upheld the color-line and maintain white supremacy. Hopkins understood the color-line as the invisible yet powerful social divide structured to separate the races, which it was so fiercely guarded and violently policed in the turn of the century. The Racial Contract was being rewritten at the time, ushering in more lynching and stronger de jure segregation to maintain the racing of space. The title keeps with the biblical

¹¹¹ Molly Godfrey, “Of One Blood: Humanism, Race, and Gender in Post-Reconstruction Law and Literature,” *CLA Journal*, vol. 59, no. 1, College Language Association, (2015), 47–74, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/44325903>, 64.

belief that all human beings are “of one blood,” but Hopkins specifies that the original blood of all humans was black. The story begins in America, focusing on Reuel’s racial passing, and culminates in Africa with his discovery of a hidden city that doubles as a metaphor for his hidden identity. In selecting “*the Hidden Self*” as a subtitle, Hopkins settled on a trope as unfixed as the book’s twin metaphor of blood. In the figure of Aubrey Livingston, Hopkins exposes the hidden self at the foundation of Anglo-American subjectivity and the suppression of the truth of miscegenation upon which the color line depends. The “hidden self” serves simultaneously as a metaphor for the suppressed history of oppressive social and familial relations under the institution of slavery.

Hopkins utilized concepts utopia and Ethiopianism because they allowed for a convincing construction of a counternarrative to the Racial Contract. Hopkins’ novel was directed at an African American audience, and John Gruesser noted in his book, *Black on Black: Twentieth-Century African American Writing about Africa*, that *Of One Blood* was “the earliest known twentieth-century fictional accounts of the continent by a black American writer, this generic hybrid claimed Africa as the origin of Western civilization over eighty years before the unfolding of recent debates over Afrocentrism.”¹¹² Gruesser argues that Hopkins signifies on the conventions of white writing about the continent in order

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to “produce an Ethiopianist fantasy for her black middle-class audience that restores to Africa its former greatness and addresses contemporary American race issues.”¹¹³ Ethiopianism had a

¹¹² John Cullen Gruesser, *Black on Black: Twentieth-Century African American Writing about Africa*, (Lexington, KY: University Press of Kentucky, 2000), 40.

¹¹³ Gruesser, *Black on Black: Twentieth-Century African American Writing about Africa*, 34.

profound influence on black American literary depictions of Africa. The movement provided a powerful discourse to the pervasive white supremacist propaganda of the day. Most importantly, as Gruesser correctly analyzed, its “promise of a glorious future for black people, Ethiopianism offered African American writers a means of looking beyond the present.”¹¹⁴ Writing to a black middle-class audience, the science-fiction aspect of utopia and Utopianism served as a bright light in times of racism and legal discrimination in America.

In the U.S. concepts of Ethiopianism, African Americans were seen as the leaders of the coming redemption of Africa, exactly envisioned through Hopkins’ novel. Martin Japtok’s article, “Pauline Hopkins’s ‘Of One Blood’, in Africa, and the Darwinist Trap” argues for the paradox of an African colonial adventure story. Hopkins’ novel, for Japtok,

On the one hand, it advocated racial pride and racialism (the common fate and implicit solidarity of all people of African descent); on the other hand, it saw Africa as needy of change on Western, even imperialist, terms. The paradoxes of Ethiopianism turn out to be the paradoxes of Hopkins's novel, informed by Darwinism and the notion of progress.¹¹⁵

Although Hopkins never formally addresses the ambiguity of the novel’s colonial story, the paradox does not hold weight since Telassar’s symbolic importance goes beyond material progress. It is built out of historical truths, thus becoming a more tangible utopia for African Americans to aspire to. Jalondra Davis has an opposing analysis of Hopkins’ Ethiopianism. In the article, “Utopia and the Gendered Past in Pauline Hopkins’ *Of One Blood; Or, the Hidden Self*, Davis argues that Ethiopianism is a cyclical view of black history that identifies African diasporas as descendants of a great African civilization, in which original African greatness is lost but destined to be restored.”¹¹⁶ Ethiopianism, in this sense, embraces a progressive narrative

¹¹⁴ Gruesser, *Black on Black: Twentieth-Century African American Writing about Africa*, 34.

¹¹⁵ Martin Japtok, “Pauline Hopkins’s ‘Of One Blood’, Africa, and the ‘Darwinist Trap,’” *African American Review*, vol. 36, no. 3, (2002), 403–15, *JSTOR*, <https://doi.org/10.2307/1512204>, 407.

¹¹⁶ Davis, “Utopia and the Gendered Past in Pauline Hopkins’ *Of One Blood; Or, The Hidden Self*,” 9.

by predicting a new rise of Africa and its descendents. Literary “Afrotopias,” as Davis calls them, share the impulses of Ethiopianism by the desire to counter images of African and black inferiority that the Racial Contract maintains. This reading of the novel correctly works to oppose the Racial Contract, which was Hopkins’ goal all along.

The *Colored American Magazine* served as a platform for Hopkins’ political agenda. The magazine was a resource for the increasingly mobilized black organizations that worked to rally the masses against de jure segregation, and the violence used to rewrite and maintain the Racial Contract. In *Reconstructing Womanhood: The Emergence of the Afro-American Woman Novelist*, a major contribution to the resurgence of interest in Hopkins in the 1980s, Hazel V. Carby profitably reads *Of One Blood* as part of a wide range of early-twentieth-century intellectual discourses. The reception of the novel sits within “The network of these relations between *Of One Blood* and other, nonfictional, articles in the *Colored American Magazine* indicated the extent of an intertextual coherence, achieved under Hopkins’s literary editorship, which aimed at the reconstruction of a sense of pride in an African heritage.”¹¹⁷ Those nonfiction articles were intentionally published alongside Hopkins’ work. In the same issue as *Of One Blood*, the *Colored American Magazine* published an article entitled, “Ethiopians of the Twentieth Century.”¹¹⁸ In a hostile takeover, Booker T. Washington bought the *Colored American Magazine* in 1904, just one year after Hopkins’ novel was serialized. Washington viewed the magazine as a “means to counter his opponents... the *Colored American Magazine* became an important proxy in one of the defining conflicts in twentieth-century African American political culture.”¹¹⁹

Hopkins’ politics aligned with W.E.B Du Bois, the theoretical and political rival of Washington,

¹¹⁷ Hazel V. Carby, *Reconstructing Womanhood: The Emergence of the Afro-American Woman Novelist*, (New York City, NY: Oxford University Press, 1987), 159-160.

¹¹⁸ Japtok, “Pauline Hopkins’s ‘Of One Blood’, Africa, and the ‘Darwinist Trap,’” 406.

¹¹⁹ Ira Dworkin, “Literary Cultures: The Black Press, Pauline E. Hopkins, and the Rewriting of Africa,” *Congo Love Song: African American Culture and the Crisis of the Colonial State*, (University of North Carolina Press, 2017) 139–62. JSTOR, http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.5149/9781469632728_dworkin.11, 152.

and because of that Washington fired Hopkins months after his acquisition. This situates Hopkins' nonfiction and fictional work within the African American political scene, as well as the larger string of black political thought since Du Bois' *Souls of Black Folk* influenced *Of One Blood*, and Mills took from Du Bois' theoretical conceptions of the color-line, black consciousness, and the veil.

Reuel returns to the hidden city but ultimately does not take up the mantle to distribute Telassar's wealth and progress with the diaspora, leaving an ambivalent ending. King Ergamenes and Queen Candace rule over Telassar despite the appearance of a happy conclusion are darkened with "serious apprehension, the advance of mighty nations penetrating the dark, mysterious forests of his land. 'Where will it stop,' he sadly questions. 'What will the end be?'"¹²⁰ Reuel dreads the inevitable approach of the white man. He enjoys the advanced African civilization while educating his people "all that he has learned in years of contact with modern culture,"¹²¹ that is the culture of the colonizers. Reuel's decision to teach Telassar of Western culture and religion is contradictory, since if their civilization is superior they need not convert to Western ideologies. Reuel's redemption in the experience of journeying to an African homeland, discovering black pride, and establishing a home is overshadowed by his decision to keep Telassar hidden rather than the possibility of opening their civilization to the world, and working to end white supremacy.

Reuel's journey and return to an Africa that is rich in history, philosophy, and spirituality provides a link for contemporary black African Americans, especially after the abolition of enslavement. Through an emphasis on Ethiopia's past greatness and present day advancements, Hopkins creates a story which celebrates black people and their contributions to culture and

¹²⁰ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 193.

¹²¹ Hopkins, *Of One Blood: Or, the Hidden Self*, 193.

civilization. Restoring history and identity to the diaspora who were subjected to forced displacement and exploitation, the utopia of Telassar offers a reality in which African people and culture has not been lost nor oppressed, allowing them to conceive of their own greatness and pride. Its goal is to correct the view of black Americans, and Africans in general, as inferior and ignorant people born to be oppressed and enslaved. The novel is removed from contemporary America in order to criticize the injustices of the Racial Contract. If Telassar resembles most utopias in presenting a society whose excellent sociopolitical arrangement stands as an opposite to the racist social order of society everywhere, its very existence counters the ongoing injustice of white supremacist thinking and the historical injustice of the loss of homeland. This mystical counter narrative looks towards Africa and its past as a source of ancestral pride and a hopeful future.